

Application of Digital Technologies in the Oil and Gas Sector: Trends and Risks

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ABSTRACT

The growing demand for oil requires the development of renewable energy resources, the improvement and optimization of existing technologies, which is practically impossible without the application of digital technologies. Currently, almost all of the world's leading oil and gas companies shape their development strategies based on the use of digital transformation. Although a positive trend in digital transformation is observed among the leading companies in the global oil and gas industry, there are still a number of unresolved issues that complicate the formation of digital platforms. The article examines the current state of digital technology adoption in the oil and gas sector and analyzes emerging trends in this field. Key digital solutions employed in the industry include artificial intelligence, machine learning, the Internet of Things, cloud computing, big data analytics, digital twins, robotics, drones, blockchain, and other digital ecosystems. The research indicates that digital solutions are widely implemented to optimize industry operations and enhance management effectiveness. The factors contributing to the effectiveness of digital technologies include flexibility, accuracy, the selection of efficient management models, reduced production costs, informed decision-making, and optimized resource utilization. Considering both their advantages and potential risks, the application of digital technologies in a complex sector like oil and gas highlights the need for continued research in this area.

Key words: *Oil-gas industry, Digital transformation, Digital technology, Artificial intelligence.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, significant dynamics in the application of digital technologies in the oil and gas industry are forming a new environment called digital oil and gas ecosystems. According to Technavio forecasts, the oil and gas market will grow to \$59 billion in 2027 [1]. According to forecasts of the International Energy Agency, the expected increase in oil consumption worldwide will reach 105.7 million barrels by 2028 [2]. For this very reason, leading companies are applying digital technologies to various production chains [3]. At all times in the oil and gas industry, there has always been a need to reduce risks and uncertainty in the process of oil and gas production, especially in the final stages of processing, field development and management decisions. In general, if it is possible to give such a classification, digital technologies in the oil and gas industry are mainly aimed at solving two problems: increasing oil production and reducing operational costs as much as possible [4,5].

Although there is a positive trend regarding digital transformations in the leading oil and gas industry companies in the world, including in Azerbaijan, there are still a number of unsolved problems that complicate the formation of digital platforms. Especially in many oil-exporting countries, including Azerbaijan, the

industry's dependence on foreign technologies, equipment, software and investments delays the implementation of digital technologies. On the other hand, digital projects need special platforms where new technologies are tested, but conducting such experiments requires a lot of funding, and in many cases, industrial enterprises are not interested in this matter.

In many cases, lack of personnel with certain competencies, competitiveness and digital development strategy and priorities are among the main reasons for implementing digital projects. From this point of view, there is a need for specialists in big data analytics, robotics, drone technologies, programming, 3D-modeling, as well as emerging fields related to digitization [6]. The lack of a single standard in the use of Internet of Things technologies and the many difficulties in the digital transformation of existing production processes are considered important factors [7].

According to forecasts, the level of digitization in the oil and gas sector will increase by an average of 16.56% per year between 2022 and 2027 [1]. Artificial intelligence, machine learning, internet of things, cloud computing, smart materials, big data, digital twin, robotization, drones, blockchain, and other digital ecosystems are considered the main digital solutions used in the oil and gas sector [1,8]. According to Gartner's 2021 research results, artificial intelligence continues to rapidly consolidate its position in the oil and gas sector [9]. The literature analysis shows that the problems of digitization and digital transformations have been widely studied from different aspects. In addition, there is a need to study the application of digital technologies, especially to the oil and gas industry.

TRENDS IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

The issue of increasing the efficiency of oil and gas industry enterprises due to digital transformation is considered urgent, but it is important in two contradictory trends in the development of this field. On the one hand, the increase in the need for oil and gas in the world increases the demand for energy carriers. On the other hand, enterprises operating in this field are constantly developing in a competitive environment and constantly face various crises and lower energy prices in the world. In this regard, digital transformation can be seen as a factor of increasing the competitiveness of oil and gas industry enterprises. In this fact, it is necessary to take into account that the oil and gas sector is the largest consumer of high-tech products in the world. It is known that many technologies of the information technology industry were initially developed on the basis of the order of the oil and gas industry enterprises and later became available to a wider audience of users. Currently, the development of digital technologies for the oil and gas industry continues at a rapid pace. Development of cloud applications, big data analysis, intelligent data analysis methods, Internet of things applications, etc. all of this is focused on gathering and processing information, ultimately allowing more effective solutions to be developed.

Taking into account the main trends, from a practical point of view, the digital transformation of oil and gas industries is divided into 3 stages:

- automation, i.e. implementation of constant remote monitoring and control;
- creating a digital twin of the deposit to predict possible situations and choose the most profitable one;
- implementation of automatic management in "real time" mode [10].

Currently, digitization is considered the main trend of the development of the modern economy. Although digital transformation is seen as a factor of increasing responsibility and income, high-tech products and technologies are not only designed to facilitate work processes and communication between people, but also directly focus on increasing production efficiency. In this regard, the investigation of digital transformations in the oil and gas sector is one of the urgent issues.

Digital transformation also opens up new opportunities for scientific research. In a number of research studies, the possibilities of applying digital technologies in the oil and gas sector, trends, advantages and disadvantages in this field have been investigated [11]. In study [12] examines the impact of digital technologies on the energy sector, provides an overview of current trends and emerging technologies. Research shows that digital transformation has the potential to significantly improve the efficiency, sustainability and sustainability of the energy sector.

In study [13], the analysis of modern approaches in digitalization of the oil and gas industry was considered. The current applications of traditional technologies used in the oil industry are examined and the possibilities of applying innovative digital tools and systems that can increase the efficiency of operations and reduce costs, risks and environmental impacts are explored. A number of digital technologies, including the Internet of Things, robotics, drones and UAVs, big data analytics, etc. possibilities, advantages and risks of application in the oil and gas industry have been investigated in detail. In study [14] is devoted to the analysis of problems of digitalization of oil and gas production. Taking into account the advantages of digital technologies, it was recommended to implement the project of digitalization of oil and gas wells with the use of fiber-optic technologies. The advantages and potential risks of the application of digital technologies were analyzed.

The directions of digital transformation in the oil and gas industry include: smart platform, digital storage, remote service, diagnostic service, pipeline monitoring, business process optimization, effective decision making, software optimization, etc.

The heads of more than 200 oil and gas companies surveyed by the consulting company Accenture consider the digital transformation of the company to be the most important component of maintaining competitiveness. Analysts of the BirlaSoft company dealing with digital technologies presented the possible results of the digital transformation in the studied sector in their report. According to estimates, effective digital transformation of oil and gas enterprises allows to reduce operating costs by 12-20% and increase production efficiency by 8-12% [16]. In addition, it is predicted that there will be an increase in indicators such as productivity, labor protection and environmental protection in parallel. According to McKinsey's forecast data on "Digital strategy", the use of publicly available technologies in the oil and gas industry alone can allow industrial enterprises to earn 240-520 billion dollars a year [8]. According to the results of a survey conducted among IT managers of international oil and gas companies, artificial intelligence and Internet of Things solutions determine the future development directions of companies [8,9].

According to the forecasts of the World Economic Forum held in 2017, by 2025, the digital transformation of oil and gas enterprises can generate profits of 1.6-2.5 trillion dollars for the industry, its customers and society as a whole [15]. The heads of more than 200 oil and gas companies surveyed by the consulting company Accenture consider the digital transformation of the company to be the most important component of maintaining competitiveness. Analysts of the BrilaSoft company dealing with digital technologies presented the possible results of the digital transformation in the studied sector in their report. According to estimates, effective digital transformation of oil and gas enterprises allows to reduce operating costs by 12-20% and increase production efficiency by 8-12% [16]. In addition, it is predicted that there will be an increase in indicators such as productivity, labor protection and environmental protection in parallel. According to McKinsey's forecast data on "Digital strategy", the use of publicly available technologies in the oil and gas industry alone can allow industrial enterprises to earn 240-520 billion dollars a year [8]. According to the results of a survey conducted among IT managers of international oil and gas companies, artificial intelligence and Internet of Things solutions determine the future development directions of companies [8,9].

The growing demand for oil requires the development of renewable energy resources, improvement and optimization of existing technologies, which is practically impossible without the application of digital technologies. In the current conditions, digital solutions become priority areas for increasing the efficiency of companies' activities. Today, almost all the world's leading oil and gas companies form their development strategy based on the use of digital transformation.

RISKS OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATIONS

In addition to the advantages of digital technologies, there is the need to ensure information security and data confidentiality, infrastructure requirements and increase the level of professionalism of personnel, the need to ensure the reliability and stability of new systems and technologies, etc. causes a number of problems and deficiencies. In particular, the development and application of artificial intelligence systems in complex and potentially hazardous industries such as the oil and gas industry poses significant challenges and uncertainties. This is especially evident when it is necessary to quickly and accurately solve problems arising

in unexpected situations. In addition, the development and implementation of reliable and accurate digital models that can be used in artificial intelligence control systems is a very complex issue. This requires serious research and knowledge about the operation of hybrid systems that can take into account the human factor, as well as algorithms for analyzing and solving problems. Most importantly, the transformation from human management to artificial intelligence management is in itself a complex social, psychological, technological, ethical, etc. creates problems. This process can be quite complex and require significant time and resources, especially considering that many functions performed by humans today, such as decision-making, must be outsourced to artificial intelligence.

The main problems in the application of intellectual technologies are the lack of sufficient funding by companies and the state, the lack of a sufficient number of qualified and competent personnel, the lack of a single standard for the use of digital technologies, the organization of activities according to the principles of traditional mining, and a number of other problems. With sufficient funding of scientific research in the field of digitization of oil fields, this problem can be solved in many cases. Accordingly, the creation of appropriate fields for the development of technologies and the implementation of experiments can allow to obtain more effective results. Looking at the experience of Western countries, it is clear that this approach and method is effective for the application of digital technologies and high-tech equipment in production.

CONCLUSION

The oil and gas industry is of strategic importance for the world economy as a whole and is the basis of individual governments' economies. At the same time, the efficient development of this production area largely depends on the application of new technologies, especially digital technologies. The processes related to the production of energy resources, their transportation and processing, purchase and sale, and the establishment of business relationships, as well as the management of oil and gas industry enterprises, human resources are highly labor intensive, and digitalization significantly increases the efficiency of production and business processes in the studied area. IoT, cloud computing, artificial intelligence and big data etc. application of information technologies allows industrial enterprises to obtain more accurate information and analyze them in real time. This technologies helps to optimize oil and gas extraction, production, processing and transportation processes, as well as allows for quick response to changes in operating conditions, improved planning and predicting. The article examines the current situation of digital transformations in the oil and gas sector, the possibilities of using digital technologies, and the analysis of potential risks. The literature review shows that digital transformation is widely used to increase the efficiency of oil and gas industry activities, decision-making, and management. It can be considered that the implementation of initiatives such as innovations brought by digital technologies, ecology, climate change, ensuring the health and safety of employees will completely change the ecosystem of the oil and gas industry. The research results show that considering the advantages and potential risks, the application of digital technologies in the oil and gas industry needs to be analysed in different aspects in future studies.

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